

Foreign diseases among young people

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Annotation: The author turns to the study of individual preventive measures implemented abroad in order to combat negative factors that threaten the criminological security of the education sector. We are talking about the prevention of suicides of schoolchildren and students, extremism among students, drug addiction, substance abuse and alcoholism among participants in educational relations.

Key words: criminological safety of education, criminogenic threats, foreign criminological prevention, fight against antisocial phenomena.

Introduction

In order to ensure the criminological safety of the education system, development of an effective system is required counteracting various criminal activities and preventing certain threats to the criminological safety of education criminogenic factors that threaten the security of the educational environment. For this it seems appropriate to pay attention to the experience of foreign countries struggling with certain illegal, asocial phenomena existing in the field of education (threats) [1, p. 3].

To criminal and criminogenic threats to the education sector, in addition to crime, should be attributed to suicidal influence on students; involving students in extremist groups; the spread of criminal subculture among schoolchildren and students; drug addiction, substance abuse and alcoholism of participants in educational relations; schoolchildren and students leaving school without further education; homelessness and vagrancy of adolescents and much more.

— implementation of school preventive programs, the participants of which are not only students, but also their parents and teachers. A mandatory element of these programs are recommendations and practical advice on suicidal topics: how to recognize a person who is ready to commit suicide, what help can be provided to such a person, and are also given addresses of organizations employing qualified specialists in the field of suicide prevention;

— development and implementation of special government programs to reduce suicidal activity among adolescents and young adults (USA). One of these programs is the introduction in society of the so-called “green cards”: everyone has the right to receive a special card that provides the person with a number of direct and immediate options, including calling a psychiatrist or hospitalization. "Green Card" designed primarily for people who faced the problem of suicide for the first time;

— creation and sponsorship of suicide prevention centers (Great Britain, Belgium, USA). The first such centers were created at the beginning of the 20th century, and their initial goal was not prevention, but providing assistance to those people who have already attempted suicide, but managed to save. Later the named centers became also perform a preventive function. For example, in the USA more such centers have been created 200, and they have different names (“Center suicide prevention”, “Helpline”, “Suicide Crisis Center”, “National Salvation - League of Life”, etc.). Despite the different names, prevention centers have the same purpose;

— development of centers for studying the phenomenon of suicide itself;

— formation of mental health services (Germany) and centers for monitoring public health. In the latter it is carried out analysis of specific suicidal cases, the reasons and conditions that contributed to a person committing suicide are identified, and modern methods are also being developed prevention of suicidal behavior in society;

— functioning of public organizations to combat suicide. For example, International Federation for Telephone Help (UK), International Association for Suicide Prevention (Australia), an association for suicide prevention (Japan) [2];

— providing psychological assistance to suicidal people over the phone, as well as visiting such persons at home, personal consultation (Germany);

— restriction of free access to drugs and means, primarily medical substances and weapons, with the help of which suicides are committed (Australia, Great Britain, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Japan, Scotland, USA) [3, p. 49].

The scientific literature notes that abroad they are constantly developing and new methods for preventing suicide among young people are being tested [4].

2. Prevention of extremism among students. The scientific literature notes that extremism has spread in the current period in almost all countries of the world and has become a global problem for modern society [5, p. 80]. Particularly active extremism began to appear among young people.

Analysis of foreign preventive experience showed that in many foreign countries the prevention of various antisocial, criminogenically dangerous phenomena that threaten safety and integrity of educational environment, great attention is paid to connection with what to combat these phenomena significant funds are allocated, and subjects of prevention regularly undergo advanced training courses in order to effectively counter a particular criminal threat. It seems that some positive foreign experience in combating such negative social phenomena, existing in the educational environment, like suicides of schoolchildren and students, extremism among students, drug addiction, substance abuse and alcoholism among participants in educational relations, it is advisable to test Foreign experience in preventing some threats to the criminological safety of education and in our country. However, such testing must be considered, consistent character and rely on the national characteristics of the Russian state.

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